

ANALYSIS OF WOMEN'S SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP USING SOCIAL VALUE, INNOVATION, AND ECONOMIC ACTIVITY

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Abstract

In life in society, women cannot be separated from every activity in it. Most people's views about women can be seen from a perspective that can be seen in general, such as the characteristics of women, the role of women in society, the family, and the education women choose. Many women carry out their dual parts by choosing to become entrepreneurs. Social entrepreneurship is an alternative that women choose to be able to develop themselves and their abilities. Awareness of positively impacting individuals, the environment, communities, and organizations has been increasingly felt since WHO and all UN member states, including Indonesia, agreed on the SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals) plan. Gender equality, quality education, and poverty alleviation are some of the elements in the SDGs. This study uses social value, innovation, and economic activity details to analyze two women's social entrepreneurship. This qualitative research describes the results of interviews conducted with two female informants who are actors in social entrepreneurship. The analysis results conclude that DemiBumi and Biyung Indonesia are examples of women's social entrepreneurship that develop by responding to existing social problems. Through educational and empowerment programs, the impact of these social entrepreneurial activities is being felt by more and more people.

Keywords: Social Value, Innovation, Social Entrepreneur, Impact, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

INTRODUCTION

In life in society, women cannot be separated from every activity in it. Most people's views about women can be seen from a perspective that can be seen in general, such as the characteristics of women, the role of women in society, the family, and the education women choose. From a historical point of view, it is found that women have played many roles. Women play the roles of mothers, wives, farmers, company leaders, volunteers, village leaders, and many more. Indonesia is one of the countries that, in general, places women to play a vital role in the political field of government, such as President, Governor, Minister, Regent, Camat, etc. This condition further emphasizes that women have a dual role in life and multiple roles in society.

Many women carry out their dual roles by choosing to become entrepreneurs. Becoming a business actor makes women more flexible in using their time. Social entrepreneurship is an alternative that women choose to be able to develop themselves and their abilities. Indonesia has become one of the countries that, in the last decade, has spawned many new social entrepreneurs. Various forms of social entrepreneurship activities have attracted the attention

of many groups, such as academics, decision-makers, business practitioners, the general public, and the younger generation. Various social entrepreneurship practices have experienced developments throughout the world. The awareness of having a positive impact on individuals, the environment, communities, and organizations has been increasingly felt since WHO, together with all UN member states, including Indonesia, agreed on the plan in the SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals).

The SDGs are a global action plan agreed upon by world leaders, including Indonesia, to end poverty, reduce inequality and protect the environment. The SDGs contain 17 Goals and 169 targets expected to be achieved by 2030. In the opinion of German & Singh (2010), social entrepreneurship combines innovative ideas for social change, which is carried out by applying business strategies and skills. Deeper than this understanding, Dewanto (2013) explains that social entrepreneurship defines some social issues and then organizes, creates, and manages social enterprises to achieve the desired changes. In line with this understanding, Alvord (2004) explained that social entrepreneurship, as a concept, was developed with a little 'out' of conditions in the community. Social entrepreneurship aims to find practical and sustainable solutions for solving social problems. These solutions require many elements to create innovation and become part of a successful business.

Gender equality, quality education, and eradicating poverty are some of the elements in the SDGs. Women, as one of the objects considered, often experience injustice in obtaining their rights, so they usually do not get equal opportunities in education and life in the household. The poverty in household life often makes women the scapegoats for this poverty, even though many women have succeeded in increasing the household economy with their skills. Women work as factory workers and laundresses; some even sell home-cooked food to help their husbands add income to the household.

Women have the right to actualize themselves. One of the ways that women can actualize themselves is through the community. Arisan, a social organization, is an example of a society where women can express and actualize themselves. The community is also a place for women to maximize the development of their skills to create economic activities that will later become part of women's efforts to develop sustainability. Involving women in the development process is not just an act of humanism. However, women's participation in development is a means to increase the dignity and quality of women themselves, and women's participation is essential in realizing equitable development. No country can prosper if women are left behind, marginalized, and oppressed.

Based on an article by Anggadwita and Dewanto (2014), women entrepreneurs participate in entrepreneurial activities, can face risks, and can identify opportunities in their environment to manage resources properly to create competitiveness. According to Benedicta, 2021; a woman entrepreneur or a woman entrepreneur can be defined as a woman or a group of women who start, manage and operate a business or business. It cannot be denied that the existence of women entrepreneurs in Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) is a reality of the economic life of most Indonesian people. The role of women as micro-entrepreneurs in the Indonesian economy is slowly developing, and has a role as "gatekeepers" for the people's

economy. Special attention to women entrepreneurs has encouraged more and more researchers to discuss the role of women entrepreneurs scientifically. Based on the results of scientific studies that have been conducted, it was found that women's activities as MSME actors can empower and create benefits economically to enable them to contribute more to economic growth.

The purpose of this study is to find out about the role of women in social entrepreneurship. This research also analyzes related to the SDGs goals that will be achieved by women doing social entrepreneurship. This study chose two female social enterprise actors to serve as resource persons. The two women are engaged in the field of a social enterprise named DEMI BUMI and Biyung Indonesia.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research is qualitative descriptive research. Qualitative research focuses on social phenomena, giving voice to the feelings and perceptions of the participants/respondents who are the object of this research.

The focus of this research is to gather information about the activities carried out in two social entrepreneurship objects run by women, namely DEMIBUMI and Biyung Indonesia. This study uses three elements in social entrepreneurship, according to Hulgard (2010), which consist of Social Value, Innovation, and Economic Activity.

The type of data used in this study is qualitative data, a collection of primary data obtained through interviews with two female social entrepreneurship actors. At the same time, secondary data is obtained from information obtained by the author through literature studies and various sources that can be used as secondary data to compile this writing.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to Benedicta (2018), social entrepreneurship is believed to benefit society. Communities comprising various stakeholders can be involved and feel, directly and indirectly, the benefits of social entrepreneurship. One of the benefits of social entrepreneurship is creating jobs for the unemployed. For example, Gojek is a startup that has the concept of empowering the community through the creation of online motorcycle taxi services. This online motorcycle taxi business is an innovative idea that utilizes existing technology. Gojek can create balance in terms of the economy through the various features contained in it Gojek opens jobs not only for motorized vehicle owners but Gojek also builds business partners together with the culinary business community, which continues to grow day by day because of the needs of the community, especially during the Covid19 pandemic when this.

Schwab (2010) revealed that social entrepreneurs have an essential role in sharing in the current economic crisis. Through social entrepreneurship, the problem of the financial crisis can be solved. It can even promote economic development, especially in Asia, by maximizing the role of society and the environment through innovative and effective business models. Social entrepreneurship is one of the choices to overcome social problems in developing countries;

Indonesia chooses to use social entrepreneurship to solve social issues. One of the leading social problems that are usually solved by social entrepreneurship is the problem of poverty. Social entrepreneurship is one of the solutions that can be applied to channel aid continuously and can even empower the poor to be freed from poverty without relying on assistance.

Dewi Meisari et al., 2020 writes that, in general, social entrepreneurship is a mixed organization, aka institutional innovation that combines the advantages of traditional non-profit organization models with conventional business organizations (companies). Social entrepreneurship can be defined as an organization that has a mission to solve a specific social problem with a business approach, namely to no longer depend on donations and grants because social mission activities can be funded more independently and sustainably through business income generated by communities, institutions, organizations or foundations.

Hulgard (2010) provides an understanding that social entrepreneurship consists of four main elements, namely:

- a. **Social Values.** This is the most distinctive element of social entrepreneurship, namely creating real social benefits for the community and the surrounding environment.
- b. **Civil Society.** Social entrepreneurship generally comes from civil society's initiative and participation by optimizing existing community social capital.
- c. **Innovations.** Social entrepreneurship solves social problems in innovative ways, including by combining local wisdom and social innovation.
- d. **Economic Activity.** Successful social entrepreneurship generally balances social activities and business activities. Business/economic activities are developed to ensure the independence and sustainability of the organization's social mission.

At least three related terms will be found in social entrepreneurship: social entrepreneurship, social entrepreneur (social entrepreneurs or people who do it), and social enterprise (institutions/institutions or social companies that oversee social entrepreneurial activities). An explanation for each terminology according to the EMES research group (Spear & Bidet 2003) definition/meaning of social elements in social entrepreneurship is:

- a. An activity launched by a group of citizen

Social enterprises emerge from collective dynamics involving community members or groups with everyday needs or goals. They must keep this dimension in some shape or form.

- b. Decision-making power is not based on capital ownership.

This generally refers to the principle of "one member, one vote," or a voting power not distributed based on capital shares in the governing body, which has ultimate decision-making authority. The capital owners are essential, but decision-making power is shared with the other stakeholders.

c. A participatory nature involving those affected by nature

Customers' representation and participation, stakeholder orientation, and a democratic management style are all essential features of social enterprises. One of the goals of many social enterprises is to promote democracy at the local level through economic activity.

d. Limited profit distribution

Social enterprises include organizations with a total non-distribution constraint and co-operatives in some countries, which may distribute profits only to a limited extent, avoiding profit-maximizing behavior.

e. An explicit aim to benefit the community

Serving the community or a specific group of people is one of the primary goals of social enterprises. To that end, a characteristic of social enterprises is their desire to foster a sense of responsibility at the local level.

Referring to the explanation above, the social element in social entrepreneurship refers to an activity initiated and carried out by residents, the level of decision-making not based on capital ownership, and clear goals and targets to benefit the community.

A new organization that is long-term or sustainable, then the organization can be referred to as Social Entrepreneurship. Conversely, if the activities carried out by the organization are limited to projects or programs that only last a few years, then it cannot be called Social Entrepreneurship. Two aspects can be used to measure sustainability: organizational and financial sustainability. Corporate sustainability means the organization continues to exist and function independently of its founding figures. This implies that the SE must have a human resource plan and a regeneration mechanism. The regeneration mechanism does not have to be formal but can be interpreted as being easily duplicated if it is to be sustainable. Therefore it is essential to keep the SE running even though later the founder will no longer be able to lead it directly. HR planning is critical to the sustainability of any SE organization, for-profit or not-for-profit. In terms of financial sustainability, if SE is a non-profit, the organization should ideally have a fan base in the form of a list of loyal donors who are willing to channel their aid funds through SE, or an SE can carry out activities that can attract donors for the sustainability of SE in the future. SE nonprofits can also start setting up business units to help sustain their activities.

One thing SE can do is understand the sustainability objectives that SE wants to achieve using the SDGs. The SDGs are based on the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), pursued from 2000 to 2015, and will guide the global goal of sustainable development until 2030. The Agenda for Sustainable Development Goals was set on 25 September 2015. The member states of the United Nations adopted a series of The 2030 Sustainable Development Agenda, which includes 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). All of the Sustainable Development Goals have targets related to the daily life of the government, either directly or indirectly. Local governments fulfill their role not just as facilitators of development initiatives but also as policymakers, agents of change, and the most appropriate level of government to connect

global destinations with local communities. The following are pictures and explanations of the seventeen Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs):

Figure 1: Sustainable Development Goals

- This one goal talks about increasing income for the poor, guaranteeing access to essential services, and protecting the entire community from all forms of disaster.
- The second goal talks about ensuring that everyone can enjoy safe and nutritious food all year round
- The third SDGs goal talks about helping people to live a healthy and long
- life towards essential services and protecting the entire community from all forms of disasters
- The fifth SDG aims to end violence and discrimination against women and ensure equal opportunities in all aspects of life.
- SDGGs six aims to ensure everyone can access clean water and sanitation.
- The seventh goal of SDGs is to ensure that everyone has access to renewable energy.
- SDGGs eight has the goal of creating decent work and economic opportunities for all
- The goal of these nine SDGs is to ensure the fulfillment of the infrastructure needed by everyone so they can be connected with the rest of the world
- Goals of SDG ten are how to reduce the gap between the richest and the poorest. \
- SDGGs eleven is about positioning cities at the core of sustainable development amidst rapid urbanization.
- The 12 SDGs aim to reduce the environmental impact on the Earth through reasonable production and consumption patterns.
- The thirteen SDGs goals relate to how to deal with the effects of global warming.
- The fourteen SDGs have goals related to protecting beaches and oceans.

- The fifteen SDGs goals relate to protecting natural resources and wildlife.
- The sixteen SDGs talk about keeping people safe and ensuring that the government works pretty and effectively.
- The seventeen SDGs talk about how to work together globally to achieve the SDGs and realize the agreed Post-2015 Agenda.

EXPECTED IMPACT THROUGH SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP ACTIVITIES

Every business, whether a commercial or a social enterprise, must aim to grow, develop, and become big. Even though profit is not the primary goal of social entrepreneurship, social entrepreneurs also need to consider the sustainability of the social businesses built. Women as social business actors need to find the expected impact in the future from the activities or empowerment carried out. The purpose of finding the effect is to compile what the organization wants to achieve and how it is responsible for itself; social entrepreneurship actors can also make sustainability plans for the activities they are carrying out.

According to Roger Martin and Sally Osberg in their book "Getting beyond Better: How Social Entrepreneurship Works," social enterprise can make a significant difference in the world when the positive impact creates a new social balance or social equilibrium.

- Creating people's mindsets to be moved to do something to change the world for the better
- Changing people's lifestyles to support solving specific social or environmental problems. The key is how to create this social balance.

Various parties can create balance. Conventional government and business are part of a community that can create a new social balance. Both can also change the world's current conditions for the better. For example, Gojek makes services that originate from innovative ideas by utilizing existing technology to create a balance in the economy. Through its various features, Gojek opens jobs not only for motorized vehicle owners but Gojek also to build business partners with the culinary business community, which continues to grow daily because of the community's needs, especially during the current Covid-19 pandemic.

Talking about social balance will involve more social and environmental problems that still need to be resolved. As part of the community or social entrepreneurs, women can solve these social problems. Through various empowering activities for women, we can help the world achieve a new social balance to change conditions in a better direction with a positive impact on sustainable social enterprises. Women, as social entrepreneurs, can create a new social balance with another approach. Muhammad Yunus, the founder of Grameen Bank, makes the world aware of the ideas and concepts of social enterprises that can solve social and environmental problems. The success of Muhamad Yunus in impacting the business he is doing has motivated many people to set up social enterprises to create more positive impacts.

According to Gunawan and Vania (2015), there are six positive impacts generated by social enterprises.

- 1) **Economic Impact;** Economic impact is the impact of creating jobs and earning income. Examples of measurable economic impacts are: Reducing the unemployment rate, especially for assisted communities, and what follows is the creation of commercial benefits from the results of social enterprise products created.
- 2) **Social Impact;** The impact in which the assisted community and consumers can positively improve their quality of life, knowledge, behavior, and creative ideas. Examples of social impacts: 1. More and more consumers are concerned about the vision and mission of social enterprises and support social enterprises in the environment or community. 2. There is an increase in the welfare and quality of life of the community assisted through social enterprises.
- 3) **Environmental impact** is the impact that is generated because the social efforts carried out have contributed to environmental sustainability. Examples of environmental impacts: 1. If the social business is engaged in processing plastic waste, then the social enterprise has contributed to reducing plastic waste 2. If the social company is involved in producing environmentally friendly products, the social interaction has also contributed to environmental preservation.
- 4) The impact of public policy is how the created social enterprise can get policymakers' attention to make regulations to develop social enterprises in the region. Examples of the effects of public policy:
 - a. The mayor organizes training to develop social enterprises at the municipal level
 - b. Regulations are made for tax relief for social enterprises that grow and develop in the region.
- 5) The impact of lifestyle changes is the resulting impact because the social enterprise has brought about positive lifestyle changes. Examples of the effects of lifestyle changes:
 - a. If a social enterprise produces organic food products, it indirectly helps the community adopt a healthy lifestyle. b. If the community assisted by the social enterprise are beggars, the social enterprise directly facilitates them to adopt a better lifestyle by working productively.
- 6) The impact of international involvement is where the social enterprise built can get attention and be used as an example to motivate social entrepreneurs in other countries to develop social enterprises. Examples of the impact of international engagement:
 - a. Attract foreign investors to invest in social enterprises
 - b. Disseminating ideas of social change to be created or developed on a regional and global scale.

RESULTS OF ANALYSIS OF WOMEN'S SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP USING SOCIAL VALUE, INNOVATION, AND ECONOMIC ACTIVITY ELEMENTS

Every woman has equal opportunities to be able to develop herself, both individually and as a group. One way one can be done to develop oneself is to join a community and do activities that are beneficial to oneself. Every woman faces the same challenges as men in running a business. Most of the challenges women face in running a business are related to competition, the costs of running a business, rent, and the problem of finding and retaining quality employees. In research conducted by the International Finance Corporation in collaboration with USAID in 2016, it was found that taxes are one of the main obstacles experienced by women; this is because they do not know clearly about the various types of taxes, tax levels, and tax rules.

Economic empowerment of women is a condition that illustrates that women can have greater control over available resources, such as income, knowledge, information, technology, skills, and training. For women to be empowered economically, women must be involved economically. The involvement of women economically will help increase the status of women so that women can make decisions in society.

The results of interviews conducted by researchers with three women social entrepreneurship actors are explained using three of the four elements disclosed by Hilgard, 2010. The three elements used to describe social entrepreneurship driven by these women are social values, innovation, and economic activity. The three women who were the objects of the research through interviews were Jessica (Co-Founder of Demi Bumi) and Westiani Agustin (Founder of Biyung Indonesia).

1. Jessica (DEMI BUMI)

The results of an interview with Jessica, the co-founder of DEMIBUMI, further clarify the purpose of DEMIBUMI's establishment. As written on the demibumi.id portal, "demibumi is a form of concern for two women named Jessica and Juliana to protect and preserve a beautiful and healthy earth for our children and grandchildren." The purpose of this statement begins with their concern for the earth which is increasingly filled with the amount of waste produced. It's not just plastic waste that concerns these two women because it turns out that much rubbish is generated in every household, such as cloth waste, paper waste, etc. For the earth's sake, it began its activities in 2014, educating a group of mothers who live near the congregational monastery of Carolus Boromeus in Jakarta. The education provided is about how to love the environment and protect the earth through the waste segregation movement and the upcycling movement. The most important teaching that is a focus of DEMIBUMI is related to the importance of starting awareness of a sustainable life. Through DEMIBUMI, Jessica and Juliana hope that what they do can have an impact by spreading goodness to many people and consistently trying to provide solutions to reduce the use of plastic in everyday life.

Sustainability is one of the goals that DEMIBUMI wants to achieve as a form of social entrepreneurship. By using the seventeen goals in the SDGs, the answer was found that DEMIBUMI is part of the eighth SDGs, namely Decent Work, and Economic Growth; DEMIBUMI creates jobs for many people to be actively involved in producing products with waste or waste-based ingredients such as fabric waste from fabric factories, from households, and other waste used for raw materials for upcycling.

The next goal of sustainable development through DEMIBUMI is SDGs number twelve; these SDGs focus on responsibility for what is consumed and produced; DEMIBUMI provides education about utilizing every product in the house to be sorted and then using the sorted waste to be reprocessed or sent to parties who need the waste to be used as raw material for production.

Based on the results of interviews conducted with Jessica, Co-Founder of DEMIBUMI, using the three elements of social entrepreneurship in Hulgard 2010, it is concluded as follows:

The results of the analysis of Social Entrepreneurship for the sake of the Earth found that social value creation by DEMIBUMI includes collaboration with the community, both individuals and in the community; DEMIBUMI conducts education about the importance of protecting the earth by reducing waste. Not only reducing the use of plastic as a form of reducing plastic waste, but the education provided is about how to use cloth waste, paper waste, and plastic waste to be used as raw materials for making products such as food wrap from used cloth and beeswax. So that used cloth which is just thrown away or more people use used cloth as rags, with education conducted by DEMIBUMI, people get the knowledge to use used cloth and turn it into a product with a sale value.

The next element is the Innovation element, the products produced by DEMIBUMI are the result of innovations carried out by DEMIBUMI as a social entrepreneurial organization. Some examples of innovations created include utilizing Tengawang oil produced in the West Kalimantan area as a raw material for making bath soap and shampoo. Another innovation produced by DEMIBUMI is the upcycle of cloth and wood waste into products such as soap containers, accessories, decorations, bags, and many more.

Economic Activity is an essential element that needs to be analyzed in social entrepreneurship. DEMIBUMI is an organization engaged in this field. Even though 70% of the activities are social, 30% are economical. Through the web and also the marketplace, DEMIBUMI sells the upcycle products it produces. The sales proceeds are used to pay the community, especially women who are DEMIBUMI's partners in making these upcycle products. DEMIBUMI has helped create jobs for women in particular, and it has helped them improve their economy.

2. Westiani Agustin (Biyung Indonesia)

Biyung Indonesia started social activities and efforts in 2018. Biyung Indonesia initiated the movement "Women Help Women Use Cloth Sanitary Pads," a collaborative exercise that seeks

to eliminate Period Poverty and aims to make women healthier and more empowered, especially in the coming month. Westiani Agustin is a woman who initiated the birth of Biyung Indonesia. The “Women Help Women Use Cloth Sanitary Pads” movement has significantly helped reduce the amount of single-use sanitary napkins waste, contributing significantly to the climate change problem.

To maintain sustainability in the "Women Help, Women Use Cloth Sanitary Pads" Movement, Biyung Indonesia makes it happen through educational activities. This educational activity provides a safe space for women to get to know themselves, their bodies, and their right to a healthy life. This activity also encourages women's groups to discuss various solutions to sexual and reproductive health problems that are considered trivial and still taboo. This activity helps women understand consumption choices that support health and access to their right to a healthy life. Besides that, the Education program also provides an opportunity for women to learn new skills, namely making sanitary cloth napkins for their use. Sanitary cloth napkins have helped women save money for four hours without having to buy disposable napkins, which can negatively impact the environment and women's reproductive health. Women's skills in sewing cloth sanitary napkins in their area can also develop into home-scale production activities and can become a new source of income for women's groups.

Sustainable development goals are one of the measuring tools that can be used by social entrepreneurship to find out what problems will be solved through the seventeen existing SDGs. From the results of the interviews that have been conducted, it can be concluded that Biyung Indonesia has sustainable development goals concerning the third goal (good health and well-being) and the thirteenth (climate action). The success in being able to increase individual awareness about the right to a healthy life and the importance of taking care of one's health, as well as success in strengthening personal understanding of healthy consumption choices and having a good impact on environmental sustainability, is the presentation of Biyung Indonesia's mission to be able to achieve the success of the SDGs on good health and wellbeing. Biyung Indonesia's mission clearly illustrates Biyung Indonesia's desire to be part of the thirteenth SDGs, namely Climate Action, to preserve the environment through education about the use of cloth sanitary pads.

Next is a discussion of the three elements of social entrepreneurship: social values, innovation, and economic activity. Biyung Indonesia, as a social enterprise, has created social value through education and training given to 820 women across Indonesia. Biyung Indonesia is also connected with eight communities that have continued to develop cloth sanitary napkin production groups, half of which are groups of women with disabilities. The innovation resulting from the Biyung Indonesia program is through education that is easy to understand through the "women's movement helping women wear cloth pads." This movement is an innovation created by Biyung Indonesia to reach more women in Indonesia to be aware of the importance of reproductive health and build awareness about the importance of the right to health for women. Biyung Indonesia, through 150 women, has initiated eight communities as sanitary napkin production groups after participating in educational workshops in Jambi, Jakarta, Yogyakarta, Sukoharjo, Papua, and West Papua, four of which are groups of women

with disabilities. Through this movement, Biyung Indonesia has produced 24,000 cloth pads. The eight communities have created economic activities for women to contribute to improving the household economy.

CONCLUSION

Social entrepreneurship is a form of business that can be used to solve social problems in Indonesia. Through the results of the analysis that has been done, it is hoped that it can help many people to have the courage to start community and environmental empowerment activities. These various empowerment activities can later be developed as social entrepreneurship, expected to impact society and the environment positively.

Every individual can act as a carrier of change, including women. With their various strengths and weaknesses, women can become agents of change for their most miniature environment, namely the family. Women and the community can develop social businesses by planning what impact they want from their social interactions.

Demi Bumi and Biyung Indonesia are women's social entrepreneurship that develops by responding to existing social problems. Through educational and empowerment programs, the impact of these social entrepreneurial activities is being felt by more and more people. However, as social entrepreneurs, they must never stop innovating and continue to impact more people and regions positively. Measuring impact needs to be considered when preparing a social enterprise development plan. Making appropriate impact measurements to be achieved is one part of how social enterprises achieve business sustainability. Finding what impact will be gained from developing a social enterprise is one of the challenges for every social business actor, especially women. Therefore social business actors need to continuously conduct education and outreach to find the expected impact on partners and the community, which are part of the social enterprise.

MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

Social entrepreneurship actors can use the elements that Hulgard (2010) presented to analyze how social entrepreneurship runs, grows, and develops. Social entrepreneurship actors can also develop plans to create sustainability from the social enterprises they build. The sustainable development goals set by the United Nations and also prepared as a sustainable development plan by the Indonesian government can assist social entrepreneurship in determining the empowerment activities they will carry out.

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